

NDAC/LO/125

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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, Xc

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In NDAC/LO/124, the results from STDDBLs after one year of observations were discussed from 'standard' simulations of 8.5 mag doubles. In the present note, for completeness, the simulations are extended to brighter and fainter systems.

1. Simulations for $H_p=6$

To check the bright-star end of the reductions, I have simulated 400+200 systems with $H_p=6.0$ for the primary component. The 400 ones in Ser. 1 have separations in the range 1-10 arcsec (single IDT pointing), while the 200 systems in Ser. 2 are with individual IDT pointings and separations 10-30 arcsec. As before, the (1-axis) position mean error was taken as 1.0 arcsec for the primary, 0.7 arcsec for the secondary (relative to the primary). The systems were uniformly distributed over the sky, and the magnitude-differences were uniformly distributed between 0 and 5 mag.

The '2-stage' method introduced in Paper Xb formally has 16 'free' C_i -parameters, but they can obviously not be meaningfully varied individually. With guidance from the 8.5 mag runs, I tried first to vary only C_4 , using the 'standard' ratios given in Table 1. From some small test runs, it appeared useful also to increase these ratios somewhat, and in 6 complete trials (with different ratios and different C_4), the best results are as follows.

Table 1. 'Standard' ratios of C_1 - C_3 relative to C_4 . (P stands for the number of IDT pointings.)

	P	Stage	C1	C2	C3
	1	1	40	1.6	1.3
	1	2	100	4.0	1.7
	2	1	20	1.6	1.3
	2	2	40	4.0	1.7

For the 'close' systems (single IDT-pointing), the C_i/C_4 -ratios in Stage 1 should be increased by a factor 1.1-1.2 above those given in Table 1, and C_4 should be somewhat below the mean S_f for correct solutions (1.4 versus 1.48 in the present tests). With such parameters, one gets 278 correct and 113 false solutions (out of 400). For the 'wide' pairs (individual IDT-pointing), the C_i -ratios in Table 1 are good, and $C_4=0.9$ is suitable for a mean $S_f=0.94$. This results in 133 correct and 61 false solutions (out of 200). Superficially, the ratio of false to correct solutions is higher than at 8.5 mag, but this is due to the inclusion of higher magnitude differences. Figs. 1 and 2 show the false and true solutions in the eclat/ Δm -plane, and they are seen to be very similar to Figs. 2 and 3 in NDAC/LO/124. The area with only true solutions is at 35-75 degrees of ecliptic latitude, $\Delta m < 3.2$. As for the computing-times, they are typically some 3 (single IDT-pointing) to 5 (individual pointing) minutes per system.

Fig. 1. Distribution of the false solutions in the eclat- Δm plane.

Fig. 2. Distribution of the true solutions in the eclat- Δm plane.

2. Simulations for $H_p=11.0$

At the faint end, I have made 200+100 simulations with primary $H_p=11.0$. The separation-ranges and position errors are as above, but the magnitude-differences were limited to the interval 0-2.5 mag. Again, a number of C_4 -values and C_i/C_4 -ratios were tried, and it was at once apparent that the 'standard' C_1 -values were too high (giving unreasonably long computing times). In the sequel, the C_1/C_4 ratios in Table 1 were halved, and then the other ratios were as good as any simple scalings.

For the 'close' systems, $C_4=1.4$ was a good choice (mean $S_f=1.43$), giving 44 false and 155 correct solutions. For the 'wide' ones, however, the C_4 -value should be as low as 1.2-1.3 although the mean S_f is still 1.40. This gives 23 false and 77 correct solutions, while $C_4=1.4$ gives 28 false ones. Fig. 3 shows again the absence of false solutions for middle ecliptic latitudes ($\Delta m < 2$).

Fig. 3. Distribution of the false solutions in the eclat- Δm plane.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the true solutions in the eclat- Δm plane.

3. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the present runs is that the procedures and results for $H_p=8.5$ are typical for the whole range of HIPPARCOS doubles. No qualitative differences are seen between the 6 mag and 11 mag systems with regard to the frequency of false solutions after 1 year of observations. (This is of course for a 'nominal' HIPPARCOS mission. It remains to be seen if *any* useful double star data will come out of the crippled HIPPARCOS 1.)